

CONSUMER'S PERCEPTION OF ONLINE AND OFFLINE VEGETABLE MARKET IN NAGPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study analyses consumer perceptions of online versus offline vegetable markets in Nagpur District for the financial year 2023-24. It investigates demographic profiles of vegetable consumers, identifies key factors influencing online vegetable purchases, and compares the competitive dynamics between online and offline retail markets. Data were collected from 60 respondents, equally divided between online and offline vegetable buyers, through structured questionnaires. The findings indicate the growing relevance of e-commerce platforms for vegetable shopping, while traditional offline markets still hold value for immediate availability and quality. The study offers insights into how businesses can adapt to these evolving preferences to remain competitive.

Keywords: Consumer Perception, Online Vegetable Market, Offline Vegetable Market, E-commerce, Retail Markets, Nagpur District, Consumer Behavior, Digitalization, Freshness, Convenience, Shopping Preferences, Product Quality, Competitive Analysis.

Introduction and Objectives

The introduction of this research paper delves into the evolving landscape of vegetable retail in India, with a focus on the comparative analysis of online and offline markets in the Nagpur District. Over the last decade, the rapid rise of e-commerce platforms has transformed the way consumers purchase goods, including essential items like vegetables. With the increasing availability of internet access and mobile technologies, online shopping has gained popularity, providing consumers with the convenience of browsing and purchasing from the comfort of their homes. Platforms such as BigBasket, JioMart, and Blinkit have tapped into this growing demand, offering a wide range of vegetables and groceries with quick delivery options, attractive discounts, and flexible payment methods.

However, despite the growing prominence of online retail, traditional offline markets continue to hold substantial value, especially for products like vegetables, where freshness, quality, and the ability to personally inspect goods are critical factors for many consumers. Offline vegetable markets, including local vendors, street markets, and supermarkets, still dominate in regions like Nagpur, where consumers often prefer in-person interactions and the immediate availability of products. The personal relationship with vendors and the opportunity to negotiate prices are also key elements that attract consumers to offline shopping.

This shift from offline to online shopping, or the co-existence of both, reflects broader changes in consumer behavior driven by digitalization, lifestyle changes, and technological advancements. The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated this transition as many consumers turned to online platforms for their daily needs due to movement restrictions and health concerns. Nevertheless, offline markets remain significant, especially in urban and semi-urban areas like Nagpur, where traditional retail habits are deeply ingrained.

This research seeks to explore the complex dynamics between online and offline vegetable markets in Nagpur District, focusing on how consumers perceive and engage with these different retail formats. By examining demographic factors, purchasing behavior, and the key influences driving consumer choices, this study aims to provide insights into the evolving trends in vegetable retail and the potential implications for both online and offline market players. Understanding these preferences is essential for businesses to adapt their strategies, whether by enhancing digital platforms or improving offline retail experiences, to meet the changing needs and expectations of consumers.

Moreover, this research will contribute to a broader understanding of how digital transformation is reshaping traditional retail sectors in India, especially in the context of essential goods like vegetables. It will also examine the socio-economic factors that influence consumer preferences and behavior in a district known for its blend of urban and agricultural communities. By analyzing consumer satisfaction levels, the study will highlight the competitive advantages and limitations of

both online and offline markets, offering valuable insights for retailers looking to navigate this evolving retail landscape.

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To study the demographic characteristics of vegetable consumers.
2. To identify the factors influencing consumers' online vegetable purchase decisions

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in Nagpur District for the financial year 2023-24. The research involved both primary and secondary data. Primary data were gathered using structured questionnaires from 60 respondents (30 online and 30 offline vegetable buyers). Secondary data were obtained from various retail platforms such as BigBasket, Blinkit, and JioMart. The data were analyzed using simple tabular methods and Likert scales to assess consumer perceptions, demographics, and purchase behaviors.

Analytical Tool

Simple tabular analysis were carried out for the present study.

3.1.1 Demographic characteristics of vegetable consumers.

Age.

Gender.

Income.

Occupation.

Purchase behavior of customer and its mode of purchase.

Monthly spending on vegetable purchase

3.1.2 Factors influencing consumers' online purchase decision Vegetables.**Likert Scale**

A Likert scale is a psychometric scale commonly used in questionnaires to measure attitudes, opinions, or perceptions. It is named after psychologist Rensis Likert.

The format of a typical five-level Likert question, for example, could be:

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree (Neutral)

Agree

Strongly agree

In addition to measuring the level of agreement or disagreement, Likert scales can also measure other spectrums, such as frequency, satisfaction, or importance, Likert scale was used for the following criteria :

1. Online shopping is an effective way to find purchase information

2. Online shopping provides easy evaluation of alternatives

3. Online shopping provides reasonable prices

4. Online shopping has quality products

5. Online shopping ensures secure transactions

6. Online shopping provides refund policy

7. Online shopping has lots of promotion offers (vouchers/gifts)

Online shopping is convenient and saves time

Results and Discussion

This study examines consumers' perceptions of online and offline vegetable markets in Nagpur district. Accordingly results presented and discussed below.

Recent years have seen significant changes in vegetable marketing, especially in urban areas like Nagpur. As consumers weigh online

versus offline options, their perceptions of convenience, quality, pricing, and shopping experience shape their buying decisions. This study explores these factors to reveal the motivations behind consumer preferences, offering insights into the evolving food retail landscape in the region.

Demographic Characteristics of Vegetable Consumers.

This section aimed at the demographic details of vegetable consumers, including their age, gender, income, occupation, and shopping habits.

Table.1 Age Wise Distribution of Vegetable Customers

Age Group	Offline Vegetable Customers	Online Vegetable Customers	Overall
21-30 Years	8 (26.67)	10 (33.33)	18 (30.00)
31-40 Years	8 (26.67)	11 (36.67)	19 (31.67)
41-50 Years	7 (23.33)	4 (13.33)	11 (18.33)
Above 51 Years	7 (23.33)	5 (16.67)	12 (20.00)
Total	30 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	60 (100.00)

(figures in parentheses indicates percentage to total)

Age Group:

The majority of both offline and online vegetable customers are in the 31-40 year age group, making up 31.67% of the total sample, online customers are slightly younger compared to offline customers, with a higher percentage in the 21-30 year age group (33.33% online vs. 26.67% offline).

The 41-50 year age group represents a smaller proportion of online customers (13.33%) compared to offline customers (23.33%) customers over 51 years are more evenly distributed, with slightly more offline customers in this category (23.33%) compared to online (16.67%).

Table.2 Gender Wise Distribution of Vegetable Customers

Gender	Offline Vegetable Customers	Online Vegetable Customers	Overall
Male	20 (66.67)	18 (60.00)	38 (63.33)
Female	10 (33.33)	12 (40.00)	22 (36.67)
Total	30 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	60 (100.00)

(figures in parentheses indicates percentage to total)

Gender:

A higher proportion of offline customers are male (66.67%) compared to online customers (60.00%). Conversely, female customers make up a larger share of online buyers (40.00%) than offline buyers (33.33%).

This indicates that online shopping tends to attract a higher percentage of female customers, while offline shopping has a more significant male demographic.

Table.3 Income Wise Distribution of Vegetable Customer

Income/Month	Offline Vegetable Customers	Online Vegetable Customers	Overall
20,000 - 40,000	2 (6.67)	3 (10.00)	5 (8.33)
41,000 - 60,000	10 (33.33)	10 (33.33)	20 (33.33)
Above 60,000	18 (60.00)	17 (56.67)	35 (58.33)
Total	30 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	60 (100.00)

(figures in parentheses indicates percentage to total)

Income:

The data indicates that high-income customers (above 60,000) predominantly prefer offline vegetable shopping (60%), while middle-

income customers (41,000 - 60,000) show an even split between offline and online channels (33.33% each). Low-income customers (20,000 - 40,000) show a slight preference for online shopping.

Table.4 Occupation Wise Distribution of Vegetable Customers

Occupation	Offline Vegetable Customers	Online Vegetable Customers	Overall
Professionals	8 (26.67)	10 (33.33)	18 (30.00)
Business Owners	6 (20.00)	5 (16.67)	11 (18.33)
Service Workers	7 (23.33)	7 (23.33)	14 (23.33)

Retired	4 (13.33)	3 (10.00)	7 (11.67)
Students	2 (6.67)	3 (10.00)	5 (8.33)
Total	30 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	60 (100.00)

(figures in parentheses indicates percentage to total)

Occupation:

Both groups are mainly professionals, but offline customers have a higher proportion of business owners and retirees. Service workers are equally represented.

Table.5 Purchase Behavior of Customer and its Mode of Purchase.

Purchase Behaviour	Purchase Frequency	Offline Vegetable Consumers	Online Vegetable Consumers
Daily	10 (16.67)	7 (23.33)	3 (10.00)
Interval Of Two Days	19 (31.67)	8 (26.67)	11 (36.67)
Weekly	31 (51.67)	15 (50.00)	16 (53.33)
TOTAL	60 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	30 (100.00)

(figures in parentheses indicates percentage to total)

Column Chart: Purchase Behavior of Customer and its Mode of Purchase.

The data indicates that High percentages of offline customers purchase vegetables daily (23.33%) compared to online customers (10.00%). Online shoppers more frequently buy every two days (36.67%) versus

offline shoppers (26.67%). Both groups frequently purchase vegetables weekly, with offline at 50.00% and online at 53.33%.

Table.6 Monthly Spending Over Vegetable Purchase

Sr No.	Amount Spent Monthly (In Rs.)	Number of Offline Consumers	Number of Online Consumers	Total Consumers
1	Less than 1000	10 (33.33)	3 (10.00)	13 (43.33)
2	1000-3000	14 (46.67)	19 (63.33)	33 (43.33)
3	3000-5000	6 (20.00)	8 (26.67)	14 (23.33)
4	Total	30 (100.00)	30 (100.00)	60 (100.00)

(figures in parentheses indicates percentage to total)

The data shows that online consumers predominantly spend between 1000-3000 Rs. monthly (63.33%), whereas offline consumers are more concentrated in the less than 1000 Rs. category (33.33%). Both groups exhibit similar proportions in the 3000-5000 Rs. range, with online consumers slightly higher (26.67%) compared to offline (20.00%).

In the digital age, the way consumers choose to purchase vegetables online is shaped by a variety of factors that extend beyond mere convenience. Understanding these influences—ranging from product quality and pricing to delivery options and user reviews—can offer valuable insights into consumer behaviour and help retailers tailor their strategies to meet evolving demands.

Factors Influencing Consumers' Online Purchase Decision of Vegetables.

Table.7 Factors Influencing Consumers' Online Purchase Decision of Vegetables

Sr No	Influencing Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Online shopping is an effective way to find purchase information	24.00	29.00	33.00	7.00	7.00
2	Online shopping provides easy evaluation of alternatives	38.52	22.96	20.74	10.00	7.78
3	Online shopping provides reasonable prices	36.67	16.67	20.00	16.67	10.00

4	Online shopping has quality products	46.67	20.00	16.67	3.33	13.33
5	Online shopping ensures secure transactions	23.33	33.33	23.33	13.33	6.67
6	Online shopping provides refund policy	40.00	23.33	23.33	3.33	10.00
7	Online shopping has lots of promotion offers (vouchers/gifts)	33.30	26.70	36.70	3.30	0.00
8	Online shopping is convenient and saves time	40	23.33	20	13.33	3.33

Online shopping is positively viewed for its effectiveness in providing purchase information, ease of evaluating alternatives, and convenience. Pricing and product quality are also appreciated, though there are mixed opinions on transaction security and promotional offers. The strong endorsement of refund policies further suggests that policies addressing customer concerns and enhancing trust are crucial for maintaining positive consumer perceptions.

Conclusion

The study of vegetable consumers reveals key insights into their demographics and purchasing behavior. The largest group of consumers is aged 31-40, with a noticeable trend of younger individuals (21-30) favoring online shopping. Gender dynamics show that offline shoppers are predominantly male, while online platforms attract a higher percentage of female customers. Income analysis indicates that high-income individuals prefer offline purchases, while online consumers mainly spend in the 1000-3000 Rs. range. Professionals are the largest occupational group in both channels, but offline shopping sees more business owners and retirees. Purchase behavior reveals that offline customers tend to buy daily, whereas online shoppers prefer purchasing every two days. Lastly, factors influencing online purchases highlight a strong appreciation for convenience, product quality, and effective refund policies, while concerns about transaction security remain crucial. Overall, these

insights suggest that retailers should tailor their strategies to enhance trust and convenience, particularly in online shopping, to better meet the evolving preferences of consumers.

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